

Industry4Redispatch (I4RD)

Deliverable 7.3

Analysis and simulation of future redispatch needs

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GLOSSARY

CAPEX

Capital expenditures

CBA

Cost-benefit analysis

CHP

Combined heat and power

DA

Day-Ahead

DSO

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Distribution system operator

EDM

Electronic data management

ENTSO-E

European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity

EPEX

European Power Exchange

EU ETS

EU emissions trading system

FSP

Flexibility service provider

GLN

Global Location Number

HVDC

High-voltage direct current

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KDE

Kernel density estimation

KPI

Key performance indicator

LAU

Local administrative unit

MFA

Register for medium-sized combustion

NACE

Statistical classification of economic activities in the European community

Net transfer capacity

Net transfer capacity

NPV

Net present value

OPEX

Operational expenditures

PST

Phase shifting transformer

RD

Redispatch

TSO

Transmission system operator

TYNDP

Ten-year network development plan

UC

Use Case

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VWAP

Volume weighted average price

WP

Work Package

ZAREg

Central Register of Installations

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Introduction

This deliverable presents the methodology applied for modelling the Austrian transmission grid and redispatch activation for the year 2030. The developed model serves as a crucial component of the cost-benefit analysis (CBA) conducted in this project in the course of work package 7, allowing for an assessment of the operational flexibility needed to mitigate grid congestions under future system conditions. Results of the transmission grid operation and redispatch optimization are presented, further results concerning the CBA and its impact on industrial redispatch participation are discussed in detail in Deliverable 7.2.

Modeling Redispatch

Literature on realistic redispatch models is scarce - which could partially be explained by the fact that parties with high interest in the topic are mainly TSOs (or national regulators), which often internally conduct their own studies. Most models focus either on market analysis, mathematical models, or the comparison between flexibility options but rarely attempt to realistically model TSO daily operations. Data availability may be further limited due to the fact that most of the time third-party data (TSO redispatch studies involve grid data and sensitive information from other/foreign TSOs) is involved, as well as due to transmission grids generally being considered critical infrastructure.

In 2020, a study assessing the interaction between flow-based market coupling and redispatch investigated the Austrian system (cf. [3]). Covering thermal and renewable power plants, it however builds upon the assumption that storage capacities are "[...] *not to be used for redispatch purposes.*" - a simplification that hinders a realistic comparison, considering that more than half of the total redispatch volume may be procured from hydro-powered plants with a considerable part covered by pumped- and reservoir-plants (cf. [4]).

Other works take a closer look at market efficiency, e.g., a comparison between cost- and market-based redispatch—often focusing on strategic behavior or gaming potentials (cf. [5]). Looking at analytical and optimization-based solutions, similar works rely on simplifications, e.g., only considering three-node example networks (cf. [6]). While this allows the analysis of observed effects and enables tracing these back to their underlying causes, these simplifications prevent direct conclusions for real-world systems.

Further studies focus on the application of complex algorithmic methods to transmission grid modeling. For example, [7] considers an iterative approach, incorporating grid topology optimization into redispatch model accounting for security constraints. However, these mostly make use of published example grid models (here commonly used IEEE and PEGASE), to study their approach without challenges imposed by missing data and focusing on the comparability (on these public grid models) with other works. Similarly, [8] - while focusing on the German transmission grid - covers a wide range of algorithmic approaches suitable for the optimization of (even non-linear) redispatch models, but is applied at most to a highly aggregated grid model.

While Austria is generally not a common focus of studies, many academic works consider Germany as their main geographical region of interest, e.g., as done in [9]. This study however models only every fifth hour and considers redispatch directly in combination with transmission grid and battery storage expansion. While this allows identifying system efficient trade-offs between measures that can, in medium- to long-term planning, target the same challenges, this combination does not reflect the operational properties of redispatch. Further, assumptions like power-to-gas assets operating "free of charge" (cf. [9]) can limit drawing realistic conclusions, since opportunity costs of such assets will commonly not be zero.

Method

The following two sections detail the methods applied while modeling Austrian redispatch for the year 2030. First, the section *Modeling industrial sites* covers the approach used to identify, categorize, and localize industrial sites in high detail. Based on various data sources, locations, available assets, and relevant techno-economic parameters are determined and further used to derive volume and cost estimations of industrial flexibilities, that can be used for the provision of redispatch.

Afterwards, *Congestion and redispatch analysis* covers how this information is derived in a similar way for conventional assets (power plants and large-scale flexibilities), followed by a detailed description of the integration

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of both industrial as well as conventional assets into a grid model, that is then used to optimize redispatch activations necessary to relieve congestions in the transmission network.

The details of the final CBA can be found in Deliverable D7.2, covering both the transmission system operator's as well as the industry's point of view, and introducing the investigated scenarios and the evaluated KPIs.

Modeling industrial sites

This section outlines how redispatch bids for Austrian industry are derived for the case study presented below. Based on a comprehensive set of data sources, first the geographical distribution of Austrian industrial sites is derived. There, the focus is laid on sites from the production sector, corresponding to sector C of the NACE. Every identified site is assigned with a thermal and electric energy demand and based on available data sets or produced goods specific technologies and units are assigned a demand as well. The focus is laid on technologies currently available and in place (state: 2025).

The derived comprehensive list of industrial sites in Austria is then filtered to identify sites able to bid flexibility for redispatch markets. Only sites are considered, which would be able to deliver at least 1 MW of flexibility—which constitutes a conservative assumption because pooling concepts could allow sites with a lower capacity to provide redispatch as well. Finally, specific costs for negative and positive flexibility bids are derived.

Data sources

In the following, the sources used are described.

Electronic Data Management

At national level, the EDM of the Federal Ministry for Innovation, Mobility, and Infrastructure (BMIMI) offers a reliable and publicly accessible source for classifying companies and locations with over 50,000 registered companies [10]. The EDM serves as a central platform for environmental reports in Austria and thus includes the ETS and E-PRTR reports, among others. All EDM applications can be accessed via the ZAREg and the master data of the registered companies/persons can be evaluated. This includes data such as name, address, GLN and NACE code. Around 12% of the locations listed in the EDM are active in the manufacturing industry (sector C) and are therefore relevant for this work.

Register for medium-sized combustion plants of the EDM

The MFA contains all combustion plants subject to registration with a fuel thermal input of at least 1 MW and less than 50 MW and is used to monitor air emissions [10]. The MFA contains important energy-related data such as fuel heat output, operating hours, average operating load and the energy sources used. As part of the EDM, the MFA also contains all general site information (NACE code, GLN, etc.) that is also listed in the ZAREg.

European Union emission trading system

The ETS is a market-based approach to controlling and reducing greenhouse gases and works according to the principle of "cap and trade". An upper limit (cap) is set for total emissions, which is reduced over time. In practice, this is done by the member states issuing emission allowances, which are auctioned or allocated. At the end of a year, greenhouse gas emitters must present certificates in the amount of their actual emissions. If a polluter requires more allowances than allocated, these can be purchased (trade). Furthermore, all emissions and transactions must be reported and published. Based on CO₂ emissions and activity, the use of energy sources can be estimated for locations listed in the ETS. The data provided by the EU [11] is retrieved via the `pyeutl` module, a library for Python.

Workplace census 2021

Statistics Austria's workplace census records all workplaces in Austria on the basis of administrative data. Data on the activity (industry code), number of workplaces at LAU level, number of employees in the sector under consideration, municipality level and employee size classes are determined. The workplace census can thus be used to determine all locations in the manufacturing sector. For 2021, this was 35,864 workplaces [12].

Useful energy analysis

The useful energy analysis published annually by Statistics Austria (cf. [13]) provides a comprehensive insight into the purpose and energy sources used in the manufacturing industry in Austria. The final energy consumption shown is disaggregated according to four dimensions. These include (i) industrial sectors (13 sectors of the manufacturing

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industry), (ii) the useful energy category provided—a distinction is made between the energy used for space heating, process heat below or above 200 °C, stationary motors, lighting and IT, electrochemical purposes, (iii) energy sources used (e.g., electrical energy, biomass, coal, natural gas, ambient heat) and the spatial resolution at the level of the federal provinces.

Spatial distribution

The spatial distribution was derived from the approach presented in [14] using the data sources presented above. Thus, first a top-down step is performed. From the workplace census, all locations can be identified with information on the LAU, the Austrian NACE("ÖNACE") code and the number of employees. at the location can be derived. All locations in sector C are therefore disaggregated from the workplace census.

Second, a bottom-up approach is used. There, it is necessary to identify all known industrial production sites by name. For this purpose, the individual locations from the MFA and the ETS register are merged with the locations from the ZAReg. In addition, these locations are assigned location-specific coordinates by means of geocoding, which is then used to assign them to a LAU area. For a considerable proportion of the register entries, no location coordinates can be determined due to incorrect or incomplete data. In these cases, the LAU areas are assigned on the basis of an assignment table, based on the zip code and the name of the municipality.

The top-down and bottom-up data sets are matched in two steps. First, the data is matched exclusively at location level, i.e. without taking energy into account. This means that for each unique location from the bottom-up dataset, the algorithm searches for a corresponding location from the top-down dataset. For a successful assignment, the NACE code and the LAU code of two data points must match. The algorithm takes into account the information content of the existing NACE codes in the bottom-up dataset and assigns higher-value NACE codes (class) first, before assigning those with lower information content (group, division). The merged dataset thus contains clearly identified (bottom-up data points with assigned top-down data points) as well as disaggregated locations (only top-down data points).

Figure 1: Visualization of thermal energy demand per NACE sector in Austria derived from the method described above and presented in Knecht et al. [14].

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Bid generation and techno-economic parameters

To determine costs for flexibility bids from different industrial technologies, economic and technical parameters are required. In the following section/table, the applied parameters are summarized. Costs are mainly driven by fuel consumption – especially those related to the consumption of natural gas and costs of (carbon dioxide) emission certificates. While calculating bids, the same costs as for conventional plants were assumed (compare Table 2). Regarding the technical parameters, the following assumptions were included:

Table 1: Overview of technology parameters, applied to derive industrial flexibility bid sizes and costs.

Technology	Efficiency	Typical load
gas turbine	electric: 33%	90%
chp plant (engine)	electric: 45%	90%
chp plant (general)	electric: 20%	90%
chp plant (general)	overall: 90%	90%
electric boiler	thermal: 99%	0%
heat only boiler	thermal: 95%	not used

A typical load factor of 90% corresponds to a possible increase of load generation (or consumption) of 10% and decrease of 90% for every considered hour. Here, the following simplification was assumed: a constant operation of the described energy supply technologies in every considered hour. In reality the availability of energy supply technologies for redispatch bids would be influenced by factors such as order situation, maintenance activities, etc. The bid costs were derived based on the methods presented in Knöttner et al. [15]

Furthermore, flexibility from industrial processes was included. This assessment was based on Traninger and Knöttner [16]. One site performing chlorine electrolysis, nine sites producing concrete, three sites with wood grinders in the paper industry, as well as three sites with electric arc furnaces were included. For those assets it was assumed, that temporarily a 100% reduction of the load consumption was possible. As long as the reduction does not impact the overall amount produced, this flexibility is assumed to be offered for 0 EUR/MWh.

Congestion and redispatch analysis

This section outlines the architecture and implementation of the redispatch simulation model designed to evaluate the Austrian power system in 2030. The approach combines forward-looking system assumptions, spatial and technical asset modeling, and power system optimization to simulate and quantify redispatch needs and options. It serves as the structural overview, with detailed methods provided in the subsections that follow. Figure 2 shows the high level approach of the overall modeling pipeline.

While the geographical focus of this study is placed on Austria, considerable impacts of international supply-/demand-situations onto Austrian transmission grid flows can already be observed today. This necessitates the consideration of such effects also in the future model year. Further, Austrian assets are activated in collaboration with foreign assets, providing "paired" flexibility to support the efficient resolution of congestions in Austria, or often times in neighboring countries (e.g., for Germany, cf. [17]). In order to be able to properly model and capture such effects, the transmission grid model (and all conventional assets) spans Europe, and the grid optimization also considers foreign congestions as well as flexible assets in other European countries.

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Figure 2: High-level outline of the overall step-wise modeling approach.

The modeling approach integrates four key building blocks: (1) system-wide assumptions from the TYNDP 2024, including installed generation capacities by bidding zone and technology; (2) an asset database specifying location, technology type, and operational parameters; (3) a European transmission grid model; and (4) hourly electricity and hydrogen market results for each bidding zone.

To represent the spatial distribution of supply and demand (assets) in 2030—many of which are not yet built—asset positions are sampled using a Monte Carlo-style approach. In each simulation run, assets are positioned probabilistically within defined spatial distributions, constrained by the requirement to match the zonal installed capacities prescribed by the TYNDP. This spatial allocation is especially critical for emerging technologies, where future siting is uncertain but has strong implications for power flows, and consequently grid congestion patterns, resulting from their operation.

Once assets are placed, they are mapped to buses in the grid model. Where multiple assets of the same type exist at the same or nearby locations, they are aggregated to reduce model complexity without compromising spatial accuracy. For all non-baseline scenarios, the model further introduces industrial assets in Austria, representing demand-side flexibilities. These are assigned to their nearest transmission grid nodes and characterized by technology-specific parameters and bid behavior, as explained in Modeling industrial sites.

Next, hourly schedules for conventional assets are derived from the zonal market outcomes. These schedules, in combination with technical parameters (e.g., installed capacities, efficiencies), are used to infer positive and negative redispatch potentials. The result is a set of redispatch bids for each asset, consisting of volume-price pairs for both up- and downward flexibility, assuming that (true) costs caused by an activation are compensated.

Two complementary grid simulations are then executed in parallel. First, a post-market congestion estimation is conducted, assuming the market-based schedules for all assets to be fixed, and calculating grid loading under those, allowing only non-costly remedial actions (e.g., HVDC setpoints, PSTs). This is formulated as a two-stage optimization problem, accounting for trade-offs between the total amount of overloads across all network elements and the emerging highest absolute congestion. The second simulation includes redispatch as an additional remedial action. In this redispatch optimization, flexibility from conventional and (if applicable) industrial assets is activated—based on the derived bids—to resolve remaining congestions cost-efficiently, ensuring transmission network feasibility.

Comparing the outcomes of the post-market and redispatch runs provides insight into the necessity of redispatch activations and the resulting flexibility needs, required to ensure secure operation. Obtained results are then used in a broader CBA, discussed in Deliverable D7.2, by quantifying redispatch volumes, costs, and various KPIs across different scenarios.

Data sources

The overall modeling pipeline is based on the most recent data and result publication of the TYNDP 2024 [18], using the *National Trends+* scenario, which makes use of predefined demand and supply capacities, based on data provided by the national TSOs, and most importantly considers the heat and hydrogen sectors. While the modeling year is 2030, the underlying weather-dependent data (like renewable profiles) are based on the representative *climate year 2009*. Besides various assumptions detailed in the methodology report [18], the choices for fuel prices

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(especially gas with 27 EUR/MWh) and emission related costs (CO₂ at 113.4 EUR/t) are replicated in the determination of industrial bids, see Bid generation and techno-economic parameters.

Table 2: Overview of commodity prices, based on the TYNDP 2024. Ranges are used where different types of a commodity exist (cf. the methodology report for more details, [18].)

Commodity	Price	Unit
natural gas	27.0	EUR/MWh
coal	6.5–8.1	EUR/MWh
oil	6.8–42.1	EUR/MWh
nuclear fuel	6.1	EUR/MWh
electricity	67.5	EUR/MWh
hydrogen	61.8	EUR/MWh
CO ₂	113.4	EUR/t

The underlying transmission grid is based on the PyPSA-Eur data pipeline [19], using v0.13.0, and based on the osm-prebuilt base network), reduced to a total of 750 buses across the modeling region, without any aggregation of buses in Austria. Detailed assumptions and limitations of this transmission grid pipeline are discussed in various documentations and publications of the maintainers—most importantly (1) the grid topology does not explicitly contain explicit "wires" (a line is always used as aggregated capacity of all parallel identical lines), (2) the spatial aggregation of the grid (outside of Austria) might introduce distortions to flows, and (3) the integration of currently non-existing (planned / in-construction) cannot be guaranteed to match the (still uncertain) final state of the European transmission grid topology in 2030. To ensure compatibility with market results, relevant cross-border capacities are aligned with the NTC values¹ that are used in the TYNDP 2024. Power plants, both their location and installed capacities, are based on the publicly available powerplantmatching [20] dataset. To simplify the mapping of bidding-zones used in the TYNDP 2024 (for which no exact shape files were openly available), the zone-finder [21] tool (an API-free helper tool offered by the Electricity Maps project, [22]) was used. Remaining zones that could not be automatically matched due to different short code conventions (e.g., UK versus GB) were handled manually. Finally, zones outside the European scope of the used grid model (e.g., regions in northern Africa) aggregate their import/export as net balance onto the net demand of the European zones they are connected to².

Pre-processing

In order to determine the amount of positive and negative flexibility, offered by conventional (= non-industrial) assets for redispatch, pre-processing steps are necessary. The following paragraphs detail how assets are distributed across, and connected to, the transmission grid, as well as how their operational schedules—derived from hourly market results—are used in combination with asset-specific parameters to determine the available amount and cost of their flexibility.

Localization and sampling

In a zonal market design, expected developments of supply capacities for a future electricity system are commonly expressed in installed power per bidding zone—both when based on national development plans (or political targets) or when resulting from a electricity market model. A considerable amount of uncertainty is therefore "hidden" in the actual location of emerging new assets, which becomes especially crucial when studying resulting effects on the

¹Based on a reference grid collection for the mid-term horizon 2030, [18], that include "projects whose timely commissioning is reasonably certain".

²While this can lead to distortions, the resulting net balance is relatively low and the zones that are modified in that way (mostly Spain, Greece, Bulgaria, and Sicily/Sardinia).

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transmission grid. To capture that, a distributional sampling scheme is used that generates exact locations for each model run.

This sampling builds upon two main steps: First, all power plants from the open-source powerplantmatching [20] dataset are considered fixed, as long as their decommissioning year does not fall before 2030. Next, a gaussian KDE is used to estimate a probability density function for each asset category's location and capacity. This is then used to sample new assets, until the target installed capacity for each asset category and bidding zone is reached. For conventional assets (like gas fired power plants), this KDE is built upon the existing power plants, for renewable generation assets it is based on renewable potentials obtained from PyPSA-Eur [19] (using an osm-prebuilt base network with 3,702 buses across Europe), with demand being distributed weighted by mean power of the per-bus time series data. Explicit and implicit demand side response—which are part of the TYNDP 2024 market results—are localized identically to the overall demand.

Emerging technologies are then weighted based on an equal-weight combination of other technologies, assuming a high probability for co-location: battery energy storage systems (co-located with demand, solar photovoltaics, or onshore wind), power-to-gas (co-located with demand, solar photovoltaics, or on- and offshore wind), and fuel cells (co-located with demand). This results in around 100,000 assets across Europe, which are then aggregated (based on asset category) at the nearest bus, reducing this to around 5,500 total assets.

Bid generation

Bids of all "conventional" (which includes renewable generators as well as power-to-gas) assets are based on available flexibilities assuming a fixed setpoint originating from the day-ahead market. This setpoint is derived by distributing the active generation (or consumption) of a technology group onto all corresponding assets of a bidding zone, weighted accordingly to their share of the technology's total installed capacity in the bidding zone. An explicit exception is made for gas-powered plants in situations where the active generation is less than the largest plant, which is then set to be the sole running plant (based on the assumption that it would be able to provide a better efficiency and therefore lower marginal costs (leading to it being awarded first in the market). Starting from this hourly setpoint, the baseline is given as positive flexibility up to the total installed capacity and negative flexibility down to zero. Based on an asset's type, this may then be modified and is finally combined with a cost-based price, as detailed in Bid generation.

Table 3: Cost- and volume-derivation strategies for conventional assets. Thermal corresponds to conventional thermal power plants, except small-scale decentralized assets most often constrained by necessary heat generation (e.g., biomass) and nuclear plants. Cost terms describe technology specific variable operational costs per generated electricity (vom), approximated startup costs (startup), fuel costs (fc), costs related to CO₂ emissions (ec), as well as market prices of energy carriers (price). Market prices for electricity (price_E) and hydrogen (price_{H2}) are based on a rolling average across the past three days. All cost terms account for asset specific efficiencies and emission factors (not explicitly included here to improve readability). Resulting positive prices correspond to the asset getting paid, negative prices to the asset being willing to pay money back to the system on activation. Volume describes the share of available flexibility derived from an asset's market schedule, approximating regulatory (run-of-river), technological (max. duration of batteries), or systemic/societal constraints (non-availability of rooftop solar, or aversion against full curtailment of renewables).

Asset Type	Direction	Volume	Price
Thermal	positive	100%	Vom + fc + ec + startup
	negative	100%	– (vom + fc + ec)
Hydro Storage	positive	100%	vom + price _E
	negative	100%	– (vom + price _E)
Hydro Run-of-River	positive	-	-
	negative	50%	300 EUR/MWh
Battery Storage	positive	15%	vom + price _E
	negative	15%	– (vom + price _E)
Power-to-Gas	positive	100%	price _{H2} – (vom + price _E)

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	negative	100%	vom - priceH2
Wind	positive	-	-
	negative	50%	0 EUR/MWh
Solar	positive	-	-
	negative	25%	0 MWh

Here the costs most importantly include "fuel" usage—where the "fuel" can also be electricity (for power-to-gas or storage assets). This "fuel" usage is based on a three-day rolling average market price (looking into the past), describing potential revenues related to additional stored energy (when offering negative redispatch) or, respectively, opportunity costs of reduced storage levels (when offering positive redispatch). Renewable generation assets are only able to provide negative redispatch—in the form of curtailment. Solar photovoltaics are limited to 25% of their total available flexibility (assuming rooftop assets to not be available for redispatch, and further not all remaining utility scale assets being fully available for redispatch), and run-of-river power plants are limited to 50% of their total available flexibility (accounting for potential limitations in flexibility due to water- or river-flow constraints) and penalized, by including a virtual cost penalty of 300 EUR/MWh, to only be used as a measure of last resort (accounting for societal/political preference to limit curtailment of these if possible). Batteries are limited to offering only 15% of their total flexibility, accounting for reduced availability due to constraints from other markets (e.g., balancing), partial non-availability for redispatch of decentralized batteries, as well as storage-level related constraints to ensure longer activations. Finally, nuclear power plants are prohibited from being activated for redispatch³.

Bids with a volume below 1 MW, or 5% of an asset's installed capacity⁴, are removed accounting for bid-size limitations and technical constraints near full load. Gas and oil-fired plants further receive a penalty of 50 EUR/MWh for positive redispatch when offering from no generation, offering a rough approximation of increased startup-related costs—a simplification that is necessary to achieve reasonable overall model run times, compared to properly modeling startups using a MILP formulation.

Grid optimization

Due to the non-harmonized and mostly confidential way(s), redispatch activations are optimized, no clear approach can be directly replicated. To model this step in a realistic way, three key elements are considered:

1. A considerable amount of redispatch may be activated in Austria to relieve congestions in neighboring countries,
2. redispatch should be activated in a cost-minimal way, and
3. as far as possible, no excess activations should be made.

To properly account for (1), congestions in neighboring countries are considered in addition to those of transmission lines within Austria. This is done using a 350 km radius around the border—all lines connecting buses within this area enforce their transmission capacities. In order to prevent assets that are too far away from the considered network elements, those located at buses outside a 700 km radius are deactivated for redispatch purposes. This selection of network elements and assets is used identically for both the post-market as well as the actual redispatch optimization step.

Post-market

The post-market analysis, without any redispatch activations, mainly serves as baseline to compare post-redispatch results to and further allows insights into the severity of congestions. To achieve that, results in reasonable

³Which might be a limiting assumption considering potential flexibility of modern, smaller-scale nuclear power plants, but since the geographical scope limited to areas close to Austria excludes a large portion of the overall (in 2030) existing European nuclear plants, this limiting factor is reduced and prevents distortion due to hard to estimate (realistic) cost-based redispatch bids.

⁴This is done in order to prevent extremely small bids from plants having their setpoint near full load, based on the assumption that a small deviation from that point would only arise from the fixed setpoint-allocation approach and not from real market bidding behavior.

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magnitudes are necessary—a mere power flow calculation based on fixed asset schedules can potentially result in an unrealistic distribution of line loading across the grid or even lead to flows exceeding a transmission line's capacity by a multiple of it. To circumvent such artifacts, controllable elements (non-costly remedial actions) are considered alongside the market-based asset schedules in a linear (DC) optimal power flow. To balance both the geographical distribution of congestions as well as high peak loads on only a few transmission lines, a two-step optimization is used.

First, the *overloading* of a transmission line is defined as the absolute value of flows exceeding its capacity in either positive or negative direction, for each line and time step. To allow comparison of a wide range of transmission lines (also ranging from 220–380 kV), this is then divided by each line's capacity, resulting in *relative line loading factors*, for each line and time step. For each time step, the *maximum line loading factor* (across all considered transmission lines) is defined as additional variable.

In theory, non-costly remedial actions could be optimized "stand-alone", resulting in a solution that minimizes line loading factors. However, in reality each considered country's TSO is assumed to follow a simple decision process: If non-costly remedial actions can be scheduled in a way that prevents the occurrence of any congestion at all, this will be the optimal choice; however if not, the non-costly remedial actions will be undertaken in a way that reduces overall grid stress and subsequently allows for a cost-efficient activation of redispatch on top; which might entail a selection of non-costly remedial actions that would (without redispatch) be sub-optimal. Therefore, as next modification, auxiliary slacks are introduced at each bus, which are able to inject/withdraw electricity at a penalty cost. These do not account for redispatch-specific information like potentially available capacities or costs at each bus, but just ensure feasibility using the assumption that congestions that cannot be resolved using non-costly remedial actions may be (as far as possible) solved in regional proximity.

Then, all transmission line (only of the HVACs) capacity constraints are disabled. For each time step, a weighted combination of (1) the total sum of all line loading factors, (2) the maximum line loading factor, and (3) the total penalty cost of the auxiliary slacks is then minimized. Since time steps are independent of each other, multiple time steps can be combined into a single optimization (combining their constraints and summing their objectives) model, essentially creating "batches"⁵. Slacks are weighted considerably lower than the line loading factors; while this results in a high flexibility to reduce that latter, it will—without any additional step—result in high utilization of these (non-existing) auxiliary slacks. Therefore, the solution of both objective terms, corresponding to (1) and (2), are recorded and passed to the second step.

Subsequently, both the total sum of all line loading factors, as well as the maximum line loading factor, are constrained to below the values resulting from the previous step, including a relaxation by 5%, respectively 1%. The objective function is then defined only as the total sum of all penalties. This results in around 18 GWh of annually activated "auxiliary" withdrawal/injection at buses in Austria, which corresponds to only 0.02% of the annual native demand (being 90 TWh) in the market, while removing extreme outliers caused by modeling artifacts (e.g., wrong assignment of some power plants to a node of the transmission network, due to non-availability of public datasets in that detail across Europe).

Redispatch

The, independently executed, optimization of redispatch activations is done using the same model used in the post-market flow and congestion analysis (see Post-market), with the only differences being that the transmission line's capacities are actively constraining the optimization, and that available up- and downwards flexibilities are given by the actual conventional (and if applicable industrial) price/volume bids, localized across the grid.

Achieving a cost-minimal redispatch activation during a certain hour, can be done by minimizing the overall costs of all activations. However, bid combinations exist that—when activated together—result in a net-gain for the TSO, which would lead to increased activations in order to gain "revenues". This is a known issue arising from the mathematical formulation of the redispatch problem, which is not constrained by the same limitations as the initial formulation of the (SDAC) market clearing, thereby leaving some optimization potential on the table. It is further exaggerated by power-to-gas and industrial assets, which offer substantial amounts of money for negative

⁵In the conducted runs, a batch size of 168 (a week in hourly resolution) was used.

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redispatch. While this would reduce the overall costs, increasing the overall redispatch activation (and the number of participants being activated) is not desirable for the TSO.

In order to combat these over-activations, the redispatch optimization introduces two modifications to the optimization model that is used. First, it is run using a two-stage approach, optimizing for *minimal activated volume* first, followed by the actual cost minimization that is extended by an ε -constraint that restricts the overall activated volume to be less or equal to the previously determined minimal necessary volume with a 10% margin. Second, for each hour, the lowest (most-negative) bid price difference between all available bids is used as offset and added to all bid prices. This ensures that no "net-positive" bid combination exists.

Both steps are run using a common linear (DC) optimal power flow. While in reality this would be done ensuring N-1 feasibility, this increased overall model run times by a too large factor. Therefore, the optimization does not consider N-1 feasibility and instead reduces each transmission line's available capacity to 80% of its actual capacity as a proxy. Actual values depend on Level of parallel lines and can vary between 50% (ideal parallel lines) and 100% (no affecting outages) of available capacity depending on the grid configuration and possible N-1 cases.

Results

This section summarizes results obtained from the simulations, most importantly focusing on quantitative insights into the model's overall performance. First, *Transmission network* presents results on the utilization of specific transmission lines and various observations that can be derived. Next, *Redispatch activation* showcases the variation of redispatch activations across the modeling period and all conducted runs, discussing differences between conventional and industrial, as well as between average and peak, activations. The model's redispatch cost estimates at 135 million EUR/year indicate a similar magnitude to historical data (85-140 million EUR/year, which however do not consider activations for Germany in Austria but on the other hand do consider grid reserve), lending credibility to the simulation results. Results show a total of 2.2 TWh of (positive and negative) activations for the provision of redispatch, corresponding to around 2.5% of the annual demand of 90 TWh - again in comparison to recent redispatch demands in the 1-3 TWh range between 2018 and 2024.

Specific results concerning the CBA, both from Transmission System as well as Industry perspective are showcased and analyzed in Deliverable 7.2.

Transmission network

Figure 3 shows results of the simulation looking at the utilization of two transmission lines that display a wide range of values across the year. First, Figure 3 (a) and (b) indicate different seasonal outcomes. Line CS, see Figure 3 (b), showcases high loading factors in both directions across the year, with only a slightly parabolic trend—indicating considerable North-South as well as South-North flows frequently occurring even during the same day. In comparison, line CW, see Figure 3 (a), shows a clear trend throughout the year: While flows are predominantly directed westwards during the winter half, the months April to September showcase considerable eastwards flows, resulting in daily averages fluctuating around the 0% line. Further, it shows westwards congestions appearing more frequently and with a higher impact during the winter half. In the light of the overall macro situation, it is further interesting to observe that activations are increasingly triggered to counteract East-to-West (and North-to-South) flows, which aligns with empirically emerging trends but shows a clear shift to historic information that shows that costs were incurred by countering predominantly West-to-East flows.

In comparison to daily results in Figure 3 (a) and (b), Figure 3 (c) and (d) give duration curves of the loading factor of the same two lines across the year. Especially in the positive range of values, these show both lines to be close to the allowed utilization during less than a quarter of all hours throughout the year. This can be seen in the light of the current definition in the EU 2019/943 regulation of structural congestion meaning "*congestion in the transmission system that is capable of being unambiguously defined, is predictable, is geographically stable over time, and frequently reoccurs under normal electricity system conditions*", as well as the fact that ENTSO-E ends their scale of congestion frequency already at 35% in their recent technical report regarding the bidding zone

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configuration. Comparing this against the daily aggregated values, displayed in Figure 3 (a) and (b)—which show maximal flows at a congestions level for a majority of the time—reveals another important conclusion: High line loading factors may materialize during a majority of the days, even when the hourly rate of occurrence is considerably lower—even showing times where congestion in both directions occur during a single day.

(a) Seasonality across the year using daily min/mean/max flows on the line CW.

(b) Seasonality across the year using daily min/mean/max flows on the line CS.

(c) Hourly min/mean/max line loading factor duration curve of the line CW.

(d) Hourly min/mean/max line loading factor duration curve of the line CS.

Figure 3: Utilization results for two transmission lines showing a wide range of operation: Line CW (center-to-west) is a connection from central Austria (node "Weißbach") to the West (to "Tauern" resp. "Kaprun"), whereas CS (central-to-south) showcases the southwards connection (from node "Hessenberg", passing "Zeltweg", to the area around "Obersielach"). Line utilization based on pure market schedules (dashed, red) and after the activation of redispatch (solid, green) show results averaged across all simulation runs (line), as well as minimal and maximal observed values (colored range). Positive values correspond to a flow in the indicated direction, negative values one in the opposite.

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(a) Hourly min/mean/max flows on the line CW during the winter half.

(b) Hourly min/mean/max flows on the line CS during the winter half.

(c) Hourly min/mean/max flows on the line CW during the summer half.

(d) Hourly min/mean/max flows on the line CS during the summer half.

Figure 4: Utilization results for two transmission lines showing a wide range of operation: Line CW (center-to-west) is a connection from central Austria (node "Weißenbach") to the West (to "Tauern" resp. "Kaprun"), whereas CS (central-to-south) showcases the southwards connection (from node "Hessenberg", passing "Zeltweg", to the area around "Obersielach"). Line utilization based on pure market schedules (dashed, red) and after the activation of redispatch (solid, green) show results averaged across all simulation runs (line), as well as minimal and maximal observed values (colored range). Positive values correspond to a flow in the indicated direction, negative values one in the opposite.

This can be further traced back to a dependence on the daily occurrence of certain patterns. Figure 4 displays the aggregation of results onto hourly values, comparing the winter and summer half of the year, looking at the same two transmission lines considered in Figure 3. It clearly supports the trend already identified before, with flow directions considerably changing between the two seasons. It further reveals the timing of situations that lead to an extreme change of flows during the summer half, which closely follow the shape of a photovoltaic availability profile. For both lines, this shows that redispatch is predominantly linked to congestions during times around noon. With both lines going from a central node in Austria to the West, respectively South, this relates to flows from the large East-West "route" (passing the nodes Wien, Bisamberg, Dürnrrohr, Ernsthofen, St. Peter) going South over Weißenbach, or directly coming from the East (the area around Wien or Sarasdorf) to Hessenberg. These relate to

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flows which are especially impacted by huge (partially transit) flows coming from Germany, Hungary, or the Czech Republic, and necessitate the activation of positive redispatch west (Salzburg/Tyrol), or south (Carinthia/Italy), of these congested lines.

Redispatch activation

Aggregating results across Austria, Figure 5 shows the seasonal properties of activations of both conventional and industrial assets. Both the daily peak, see Figure 5 (a), as well as average activations, see Figure 5 (b), show similarities between both types of assets. However, a considerably more consistent activation of negative flexibilities across the whole year can be observed for industrial assets, where conventional ones show lower results during the summer than the winter (e.g., February). Further, comparing activations across different simulation runs, a high similarity of activation patterns can be observed, with one run displaying a considerable deviation from others for negative industrial activations, which highlights the potential impact of uncertainties "hidden" in the location of emerging assets.

(a) Daily peak redispatch activation.

(b) Daily average redispatch activation.

Figure 5: Redispatch activations, across the year, shown for all simulation runs. Columns (x-axis) corresponds to the date, rows (y-axis) to a unique run. Each sub-figure shows results for all conventional, respectively industrial, assets aggregated in Austria.

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Outlook

The results obtained from the eight different remuneration scenarios as well as the effect of incorporating industrial assets into the redispatch process will be described and analysed in Deliverable D7.2. There, a *baseline scenario* (without industry) and a scenario considering an absolute markup of 10 EUR/MWh for all assets was compared; as well as effects linked to the variation of an industrial markup from 10 EUR/MWh to 75 EUR/MWh. Finally, the analysis examines various defined KPIs and provides detailed insights into the cost-benefit analysis (CBA), considering both the perspective of the TSO (or system) and that of the overall industry.

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